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Reinforcement Learning-Based ALOHA-Q Protocol with Slot Subdivision for Underwater Acoustic Sensor Networks

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Abstract— This paper presents SS-ALOHA-Q, a Reinforcement Learning-based MAC protocol that builds upon slotted ALOHA by introducing slot subdivision to effectively mitigate the impact of large propagation delays in Underwater Acoustic Sensor Networks (UASNs). The protocol leverages reinforcement learning to dynamically optimize channel access, enabling adaptive scheduling and responsive decision-making in highly variable underwater environments. Performance evaluation was conducted using the DESERT simulator, where a Hidden Markov Model (HMM) was employed to model underwater acoustic channel dynamics. Comparative analysis against benchmark MAC protocols demonstrates that SS-UW-ALOHA-Q significantly improves channel utilization while maintaining energy efficiency, demonstrating its potential for robust and efficient UASN operations.

I. INTRODUCTION

Underwater Acoustic Sensor Networks (UASNs) are crucial for aquatic exploration and monitoring, enabling applications such as oceanographic data collection, disaster warning, resource exploration, and military surveillance [1]. Unlike terrestrial networks that use radio frequency (RF) signals, UASNs rely on acoustic waves, which propagate effectively underwater over long distances. However, acoustic communication presents challenges. The speed of sound in water (~1500 m/s) is about five orders of magnitude slower than RF signals in air, leading to propagation delays on the order of seconds in large-scale deployments. Additionally, acoustic channels have limited bandwidth and constraining data transmission rates. Signal attenuation from spreading, absorption, and environmental noise further degrades communication over long distances, while multipath propagation, caused by reflections from the surface, seabed, and underwater objects, leads to significant inter-symbol interference and delay spreads.

The harsh underwater environment poses challenges for Medium Access Control (MAC) protocols, which manage channel access. Traditional MAC protocols designed for terrestrial networks, assuming fast propagation and high

bandwidth, perform poorly in UASNs. Contention-based protocols like ALOHA and CSMA suffer from frequent collisions, high retransmissions and increased energy consumption due to long propagation delays and spatial-temporal uncertainties [2]. While TDMA prevents collisions, it requires large time slots to accommodate worst-case delays, leading to significant channel underutilization [3].

Recent research highlights the potential of Reinforcement Learning (RL) in developing adaptive, distributed MAC protocols for UASNs with minimal communication overhead [1, 4-6]. By modeling sensor nodes as RL agents, these protocols enable autonomous learning of efficient transmission strategies, adapting to variations in link quality, propagation delays, and traffic patterns. Notably, it has been shown that RL-based MAC protocols can significantly improve channel utilization without relying on centralized coordination or prior knowledge of link propagation delays.

This paper introduces Slot-Subdivided Underwater ALOHA with Q-learning (SS-UW-ALOHA-Q), a novel RL-based MAC protocol that enhances the framed ALOHA paradigm [7], which provides a balanced compromise between TDMA's structured scheduling and pure ALOHA's random-access approach. The protocol is designed to tackle underwater acoustic communication challenges by integrating slot subdivision within the framed ALOHA structure and adapting transmission strategies through RL. To evaluate the protocol performance, we used the DESERT Underwater Network Simulator [8], a specialized framework for underwater acoustic communications. The simulation results show improved channel utilization and energy efficiency compared to TDMA, CS-ALOHA [9], and T-Lohi [10] protocols.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the architecture and operation of the proposed protocol, including its frame structure and learning algorithm. Section III presents performance evaluation results through simulations and comparisons with baseline protocols. Section IV concludes with key findings and potential directions for future research.

II. SS-UW-ALOHA-Q

The proposed protocol builds upon the UW-ALOHA-Q [4], a Q-learning [11] based protocol which adapted the framed-ALOHA for UASNs to enable asynchronous

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operation and improve channel utilization. While UW-ALOHA-Q represented an advancement in underwater MAC protocols, it faces several key limitations. First, its transmission scheme requires time slots dimensioned to accommodate data packet transmission, maximum round-trip delay, and acknowledgment (ACK) reception. Second, the frame size is determined by a heuristic formula whose efficiency varies significantly with network radius and topology. Third, in case of collisions, nodes independently adjust their frame start times through a random backoff mechanism, separate from the slot learning process, often preventing network convergence [1]. Finally, the protocol requires both data and ACK packets to share the same channel—an impractical constraint given the limited bandwidth of acoustic modems. In the remainder of this section, we describe the design of SS-UW-ALOHA-Q and demonstrate how it addresses these limitations while still retaining benefits of Q-learning.

Like UW-ALOHA-Q, SS-UW-ALOHA-Q is designed for star network topologies with a central sink node and follows a framed ALOHA approach. However, it introduces a novel frame structure with two distinct parts: one for data packet transmissions to the sink and another for cumulative ACKs from the sink, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The data transmission period is divided into equal slots, with the number of slots matching the number of network nodes (excluding the sink). Each node selects a single slot for data transmission at the start of the frame. The sink then transmits a cumulative ACK at the beginning of the second part, listing the addresses of nodes whose packets were successfully received. Unlike UW-ALOHA-Q, our protocol requires network-level synchronization. While this introduces a communication overhead, it enables higher throughput by eliminating the need to divide the limited acoustic bandwidth into separate data and ACK sub-channels.

The frame structure differs fundamentally from standard framed-ALOHA and UW-ALOHA-Q, which dimension slots to accommodate transmission times of data (T_{dp}) and ACK packets (T_{ack}) and maximum propagation delays (τ_{prop_max}). Such an approach proves inefficient in UASNs, where propagation delays typically range from hundreds of milliseconds to over a second. Instead, we implement shorter data transmission slots of duration γT_{dp} , where $1 \leq \gamma \leq 2$ serves as a scaling factor providing a guard interval to facilitate collision avoidance. To further reduce collision probability while enabling higher channel utilization, each slot is divided into n subslots. This subdivision enables nodes to find collision-free transmission strategies even with small γ values, as packets from all nodes can align at the sink without collisions when subslots are optimally selected.

The optimization of sensor node transmission strategies, including time slot and subslot selection, is achieved through the implementation of a single-state Q-learning algorithm. The single-state approach is appropriate given the star topology with a single receiver. In Q-learning, the objective for the agent is to determine an optimal decision-making policy that maximizes the cumulative discounted reward [11].

In this specific case, each node operates as an independent single-state Q-learning agent, learning to make strategic transmission decisions based on sink's feedback. The agent maintains a Q-table, which stores estimated values for all feasible actions. Initially, the Q-table is populated with random values, which are then iteratively refined using the Bellman equation [11] as the agent interacts with the network.

Fig. 1. Frame structure of SS-UW-ALOHA-Q.

The action space is defined by combinations of time slots and subslots, resulting in a two-dimensional Q-table. When a node has a packet queued for transmission, it selects slot-subslot combination for packet transmission in the subsequent frame based on the associated Q-values. The decision-making process is guided by the learned transmission policy, where higher Q-values indicate more favorable transmission opportunities. In the second part of the frame, the node receives feedback from the sink node in the form of a cumulative ACK, which serves as a reinforcement signal. This feedback translates into either a Q-learning reward or penalty, enabling the node to refine its transmission strategy over time. The Q-values are updated following the Q-learning update rule:

$$Q(k, s) \leftarrow Q(k, s) + \alpha[r - Q(k, s)] \quad (1)$$

where k and s denote the selected time slot and subslot, respectively, α is the learning rate, and r represents the reward signal received from the sink node. If the node detects its MAC address in the received ACK packet, the transmission is deemed successful, a reward of $r=1$ is assigned. Conversely, if the MAC address is absent in the ACK, indicating a collision, the node receives a reward of $r=0$. In cases where no ACK packet is received in the current frame, the node does not update its Q-table, thereby preventing erroneous learning updates due to packet loss caused by adverse channel conditions.

The decentralized nature of the proposed protocol enables the network to self-organize without requiring predefined schedules, making it well-suited for dynamic underwater environments where topology and channel conditions frequently change. However, the absence of centralized coordination means that nodes may experience suboptimal performance during the learning phase, as they gradually adapt to network conditions. The selection of key protocol parameters, such as the scaling factor γ and slot division factor n , plays a crucial role in balancing maximum theoretical channel utilization, synchronization accuracy requirements, and the convergence speed of the learning algorithm.

III. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

We evaluated the protocol using the DESERT Underwater simulator, focusing on a star topology network with a single sink and variable number of nodes within a 750m radius.

A. Underwater Channel Modeling

Accurately modeling the underwater acoustic channel presents a significant challenge in the evaluation of MAC protocols for UASNs. The stochastic nature of the acoustic medium, characterized by multipath propagation, absorption loss, and temporal variations, makes it difficult to develop analytical models that fully capture real-world conditions. To address this, we employ the Hidden Markov Model (HMM) module in DESERT, which provides a data-driven channel representation instead of relying on theoretical assumptions. Using Bit Error Rate (BER) data from the ASUNA dataset [12], we derive a time-varying channel model that reflects real-world transmission dynamics. For each recorded BER value, the corresponding Packet Error Rate (PER) is determined by calculating the probability that no more than one bit error occurs within each 7-bit chunk, as defined by the Hamming (7,4) Forward Error Correction (FEC) scheme [13]. This probability is then applied across the entire packet, considering the total number of 7-bit chunks it contains.

The channel state is classified into three categories (good, medium, and bad) based on predefined PER thresholds. For each state, the PDR is calculated as the mean PDR observed during periods when the channel was in the corresponding state. The transition probabilities between states are computed by analyzing the state transition occurrences over time. Once the state-differentiation thresholds are set, the frequency of transitions between states is recorded, enabling the estimation of state transition probabilities. These probabilities, along with the observed state durations, are used to construct the HMM representation of the channel.

Each communication link is configured as an HMM-based channel model, allowing for the prediction of state transitions over time. It is important to note that the HMM module is activated only when the physical layer successfully receives a packet, as determined by the Urick-Thorp absorption model implemented in DESERT. This ensures that the channel representation remains consistent with acoustic propagation constraints while improving the realism of network behavior in simulations.

B. Simulation parameters

The performance of the proposed protocol is evaluated based on channel utilization and energy consumption. Channel utilization is defined as the fraction of the total simulation time during which the sink node successfully receives data packets. Consumed energy is measured across all nodes (including sink), for both transmissions and receptions.

Table 1 presents the complete simulation parameters.

C. Simulation results

This section presents simulation results, comparing SS-UW-ALOHA-Q with three benchmark MAC protocols:

- TDMA – A schedule-based protocol that assigns dedicated transmission slots to each node, with slot duration: $T_s = T_{dp} + T_{ack} + 2\tau_{prop_max}$.
- CS-ALOHA [9] – A random-access protocol where nodes sense the channel before attempting transmission.
- T-LOHI [10] – A token-based contention protocol for low-power UASNs, using tone signaling to reserve channel access before data transmission.

TABLE I. SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Packet size	28 B (with FEC)
Bitrate	600 bps
Transmitting power	165 dB
Acquisition treshold	15 dB
Subslot number n	1, 3, 5
UW-ALOHA-Q learning rate	0.1
Packet generation period	5 s
γ	1.6
Central frequency	25000 Hz
Bandwidth	5000 Hz
Simulation duration	15000 s

In addition to the HMM-based channel model described earlier, we also evaluate performance using a range-based model following Urick-Thorp attenuation principles, where the BER depends on packet size, communication distance, frequency, and reception conflicts. We structured our evaluation this way because packet losses significantly impact the RL process of the protocol. Since nodes cannot distinguish between losses caused by collisions (indicating suboptimal agent actions) and those resulting from poor channel conditions, evaluating first with an idealized range-based model before testing under realistic conditions allows us to isolate and analyze these effects on protocol performance.

Fig. 2 illustrates the channel utilization for varying network densities under the range-based BER model. The results indicate that SS-UW-ALOHA-Q outperforms the benchmark protocols across all configurations. However, its performance is highly dependent on the number of subslots per slot - n . When $n=1$, the network fails to learn the collision-free transmission when the number of nodes exceeds five. For $n=3$ and $n=5$, the protocol achieves higher channel utilization, with suboptimal strategy used only in the highest-density scenario (20 nodes). The results indicate that $n=3$ is preferable configuration, offering the best balance between channel utilization and learning speed due to its reduced action space. Among the benchmark protocols, CS-ALOHA and TDMA exhibit relatively stable performance across different network densities. In contrast, T-Lohi experiences a significant performance drop when the number of nodes exceeds 5, primarily due to its tone-based contention mechanism, which becomes inefficient under high traffic loads. As network density increases, more nodes compete for channel access, leading to frequent tone collisions, prolonged access delays, and reduced

transmission opportunities. Unlike CS-ALOHA, which allows immediate retransmissions, T-Lohi's strict access control further amplifies delays.

Fig 2. Channel utilization in the scenario with range-based BER model.

Fig. 3 presents the channel utilization results under the HMM-based channel model, which accounts for realistic channel variations and random packet loss due to environmental factors. It can be observed that all protocols degrade under these conditions, but SS-UW-ALOHA-Q is particularly sensitive due to challenges in differentiating collision-induced from channel-induced losses. Despite this, it maintains superior performance.

Fig. 3. Channel utilization in the scenario with HMM-based BER model.

Fig. 4 presents the channel utilization-to-energy consumption ratio for all simulated MAC protocols in a 10-node network scenario. Again, SS-UW-ALOHA-Q ($n = 3$) achieves the best performance, demonstrating the highest channel utilization per unit of energy consumed. T-Lohi, despite its poor throughput in high-density scenarios, surpasses TDMA and CS-ALOHA in energy efficiency due to its low transmission power requirements and shorter contention phases.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we introduced SS-UW-ALOHA-Q, a RL-based MAC protocol for UASNs, that uses Q-learning to optimize time slot selection and dynamically adapt to highly variable underwater environments. To address the bandwidth limitations of acoustic modems, we proposed a novel MAC time-frame where data packets and cumulative ACKs are transmitted in separate parts of the frame. Additionally, we reduced time slot size compared to standard framed-ALOHA approach and introduced slot subdivision to increase

opportunities for learning efficient transmission strategies. Simulation results using DESERT with an HMM-based channel model showed that SS-UW-ALOHA-Q outperforms state-of-the-art MAC protocols in channel utilization and energy efficiency. Future work will explore adaptive frame sizes to better accommodate traffic variations.

Fig 4. Channel utilization over energy consumption ratio.

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